

ROLE OF EOSINOPHILS IN PARASITIC INFECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Eosinophilia, a pronounced increase of eosinophils in the blood or tissues, occurs in numerous important circumstances, like allergic diseases, parasitic infections, and cancer. Helminthic parasites are usually the common parasitic infections which cause eosinophilia apart from two enteric protozoans, *Isoospora belli* and *Dientamoeba fragilis*. Infection with helminth parasites produces immune effector responses and in a reaction to various stimuli, eosinophils are recruited from the circulation into inflammatory foci, where they modulate immune responses via sequences of mechanisms. The defence against organisms that are too large to be phagocytosed, particularly parasitic helminths seems to be the primary role of eosinophils. In this article, we will discuss some of the biological features of eosinophils and their role in parasitic infections.

KEYWORDS: Eosinophils, parasitic infections, eosinophilia

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INTRODUCTION

As multifunctional leukocytes, Eosinophils are implicated in the pathogenesis of several inflammatory processes, as well as parasitic infections and allergic diseases (Gleich and Loeferer, (1984); Rothenberg (1998). When, Paul Ehrlich noticed the affinity of cytoplasmic granules – small ‘bombs’ containing cytotoxic proteins – for the red acid dye eosin, which stains the cell cytosol a distinctive granular pink in 1879, they were so-named as eosinophils (Behm and Ovington (2000). The eosinophils represent a small percentage of leukocytes in peripheral blood in normal subjects, and their existence in tissues is primarily limited to the gastrointestinal mucosa. However, eosinophils can selectively accumulate in the peripheral blood or any tissue in the body in some disease states (Rothenberg, 1998).

The inflammation correlated to parasite organisms is a complex reaction of the vascular tissues to eliminate infection, exposition to toxins or cellular injury related to extravascular accumulation of plasmatic proteins and leukocytes, in addition to the production of cytokines from the injured tissue. It is an important component of multifactorial pathogenesis involved in diverse diseases 4. As a reaction to diverse stimuli, eosinophils are recruited from the circulation into inflammatory foci, where they modulate immune responses via sequences of mechanisms. Inducing of eosinophils by engagement of receptors for cytokines, immunoglobulins, and complement can initiate the secretion of a wide variety of proinflammatory cytokines IL-2, IL-4, IL-5, IL-10, IL-12, IL-13, IL-16, IL-18, and TGF (transforming growth factor)- α/β , chemokines (RANTES and eotaxin-1), and lipid mediators platelet-activating factor and leukotriene C4 (LTC4) 5.

In this article, we will discuss some of the biological features of eosinophils and their role in parasitic infections

BIOLOGY OF EOSINOPHILS

In the bone marrow, the eosinophils mature from the myeloid lineage of developing blood cells. The differentiation of multipotent stem cell is stimulated by specific growth factors in the dependence of the expression of specific genes that leads to the formation of different proteins, e. g. the granule proteins, that provide the eosinophils their characteristic features. Immature stem cells differentiate into an eosinophil granulocyte depending on several growth factors, such as granulocyte/macrophage colony-stimulating factor

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(GM-CSF), interleukin-3 (IL-3) and especially on the eosinophil differentiation factor IL-5. IL-5 also induces the release of eosinophils from the bone marrow into the peripheral circulation (Collins *et al.*, 1995).

The genes that code these cytokines are closely linked on chromosome 5q31 and bind to receptors that have a common beta chain and different alpha chains. The significant role of interleukin-5 in the production of eosinophils is best proven by genetic manipulation in mice. Overproduction of interleukin-5 in transgenic mice lead to profound eosinophilia, and deletion of the interleukin-5 gene induces a marked reduction of eosinophils in the blood and lungs after an allergen challenge (Rothenberg, 1998). While migration from the circulation into tissues, a stepwise interaction between eosinophils and endothelial cells are involved (Resnick and Weller (1993). As a first step the molecules adhere to the endothelium cells and counter-ligands on eosinophils then the eosinophils passes between endothelial cells. The adhesion to endothelial cells is done by means of three selectins (adhesion molecules on endothelial cells) and their corresponding ligands. The P-selectin ensures the rolling of eosinophils on the endothelium but neutrophil rolling is mediated by E-selectin. Thanks to adhesion molecules of the integrin family, Eosinophils adhere firmly to the endothelium, after cellular activation. These involve the CD18 family ($\beta 2$ integrins) and very-late-antigen-4 (VLA-4) molecules ($\beta 1$ integrins) (Rothenberg (1998).

The chemoattraction or the migration of eosinophils into tissues is started by local chemoattractant molecules. These molecules are probably the cause of both physiologic homing, in which eosinophils are directed of the gastrointestinal tract into the lamina propria, and the recruitment of eosinophils into inflamed tissues. The survey of eosinophils in tissues, in contrast to neutrophils, can be for long time (perhaps weeks), relying on the cytokines in the microenvironment (Rothenberg *et al.*, 1987). The longevity of tissue eosinophils is not known, but interleukin-3, interleukin-5, and GM-CSF inhibit eosinophil apoptosis for around 12 to 14 days in vitro and in explants of allergic sinus tissue (Simon *et al.*, 1987). However, in the absence of these cytokines, eosinophils survive for under 48 hours (Rothenberg *et al.*, 1987). Tissue eosinophils can also adjust their own survival through an autocrine pathway (Kita (1996); Kayet *al.*, 1995).

EOSINOPHILS AND PARASITIC INFECTIONS

Parasitic infections represent the second most-common cause of eosinophilia in developed nations, comprising 8% of eosinophilias in one large European cohort (Montgomery *et al.*, 2013).

In adults less than 0.4×10^9 eosinophils per liter is considered normal, while newborns have higher levels. In approximate numbers it can be said that $0.4 - 1.5 \times 10^9$ per liter represents mild eosinophilia, $1.5-5.0 \times 10^9$ per liter, moderate eosinophilia and $>5.0 \times 10^9$ per liter, severe eosinophilia (Wardlaw and Kay (1995).

In patients with moderate-to-severe eosinophilia some diagnostic studies should be performed and should be considered in patients with persistent mild eosinophilia include morphologic examination of a blood smear, urinalysis, and serial stool examinations for ova and parasites (Parrillo *et al.*, 1978; Weller (1994). Parasitic infections that cause eosinophilia are usually limited to helminthic parasites, with the exception of two enteric protozoans, *Isoospora belli* and *Dientamoebafragilis*.

In developed nations, parasitic infections correspond to the second most-common cause of eosinophilia comprising 8% of eosinophilias in one large European cohort (Montgomery *et al.*, 2013).

The normal rate in adults should be less than 0.4×10^9 eosinophils per liter, while newborns have higher levels. Eosinophilia can be classified as mild, moderate and severe with the following rates respectively: $0.4 - 1.5 \times 10^9$, $1.5-5.0 \times 10^9$ and $>5.0 \times 10^9$ per liter (Wardlaw and Kay (1995).

In patients with moderate-to-severe eosinophilia certain diagnostic studies needs to be performed and should be taken into consideration in patients with persistent mild eosinophilia include morphologic examination of a blood smear, urinalysis, and serial stool examinations for ova and parasites ((Parrillo *et al.*, 1978; Weller (1994). Parasitic infections that cause eosinophilia are generally limited to helminthic parasites, apart from of two enteric protozoans, *Isoospora belli* and *Dientamoebafragilis*, *Strongyloidesstercoralis* infection is important to

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diagnose, because it can cause disseminated fatal disease in immunosuppressed patients; its detection often requires serologic testing. Other infections to rule out are those with filarial parasites, trichinosis, and *Toxocaracanis* infection (GleichandLoeering, 1984).

This eosinophilia is due to the beneficial function of eosinophils to defend the host against parasitic helminths. This is based on several lines of evidence, including on the first hand the ability of eosinophils to mediate antibody (or complement) dependent cellular toxicity against helminths *in vitro*, on the second hand the observation that eosinophil levels increase during helminthic infections and that eosinophils aggregate and degranulate in the local vicinity of damaged parasites *in vivo*, and on the third hand the results in experimental parasite infected mice that have been depleted of eosinophils by IL-5 neutralization and/or gene targeting (Marc and Simon (2006).

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Infection with helminth parasites induces immune effector responses that are characterized by IgE antibody production, tissue and peripheral blood eosinophilia, and participation of inflammatory mediator-rich tissue mast cells (Barçanteet *al.*, 2012). In parasitic infections, although these types of responses can certainly induce pathologic reactions, they have also been implicated in mediating protective immunity to the helminth parasites. Helminth infections are associated with a predominant induction of a Th2 type of immune response, that involves the interaction of signals from the T cells receptors, transcription factors like T-bet, STAT-6 and GATA-3 and cellular interactions mediated by cytokines. The Th2 response is polarized by interleukins: IL-4, IL-5, IL-9 and IL-13 (Fallon and Mangan(2007). Activated mast cells, eosinophils and basophils infiltrate in the tissue as result of a Th2 exacerbated cellular type reaction that initiates the production of IgE and promote the tecidual eosinophilia and mast cells hyperplasia (Barçanteet *al.*, 2012). The activated eosinophils secrete the content of its granules, including main basic and cationic proteins, which are capable to destroy even the resistant tegument of helminthes, as it represents a relevant protective mechanism.

Helminthes parasitic infection leads to immune effector responses that are characterized by production of IgE antibody, eosinophilia in tissue and peripheral blood, and participation of inflammatory mediator-rich tissue mast cells (Fallon and Mangan(2007). In the parasitic infections, although these kinds of responses can definitely induce pathologic reactions, they have also been implicated in mediating protective immunity to the helminth parasites. The induction of a Th2 is the type of immune response witch is associated with helminth infections, that concern the interaction of signals from the T cells receptors, transcription factors such as T-bet, STAT-6 and GATA-3 and cellular interactions mediated by cytokines. The Th2 response is polarized by interleukins: IL-4, IL-5, IL-9 and IL-13 [18]. After activation, mast cells, eosinophils and basophils infiltrate in the tissue as result of a Th2 exacerbated cellular type reaction that starts the production of IgE and promote the tecidual eosinophilia and mast cells hyperplasia (Fallon and Mangan(2007).

The degranulation of activated eosinophil and the release of their content including main basic and cationic proteins, which are capable to destroy even the resistant tegument of helminthes, as it represent a related protective mechanism.

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These proteins perform various biological activities. Cytotoxic granules injure both the host tissue and the parasite (Bruschi *et al.*, 2008). It has been suggested that the immunoglobulins IgG and IgA are able to trigger eosinophils degranulation Hogan *et al.* (2008.). However, the presence of IgE receptors on eosinophils remains controversial. Recently, T cell has also been shown to have a role in eosinophil degranulation.

The primary function of eosinophils is considered to be defence against organisms that are too large to be phagocytosed, particularly parasitic helminths. They might also be involved in wound healing and repair, in fibrosis, and are thought to act as antigen-presenting cells (Behm and Ovington(2000). As well as host-derived immunoglobulins and gets, eosinophils might bind and respond to carbohydrate ligands expressed on the parasite surface, such as the Lewisx-related molecules, and cell-adhesion molecules similar to selectins that have, for example, been demonstrated on schistosomula(Behm and Ovington(2000).

These proteins execute different biological activities. Cytotoxic granules injure equally the parasite and the host tissue (Bruschi *et al.*, 2008) . It has been proposed that eosinophils degranulation could be induced by the immunoglobulins IgG and IgA (Hogan *et al.* (2008.). However, the existence of IgE receptors on eosinophils remains controversial. Currently, T cell has also been proved to have a function in eosinophil degranulation.

The defence against organisms that are too large to be phagocytosed, particularly parasitic helminthes seems to be the primary role of eosinophils. They could also be involved in, wound healing and repair, in fibrosis and are thought to act as antigen-presenting cells (Behm and Ovington(2000). In addition to host-derived immunoglobulins and gets, eosinophils might bind and interact with carbohydrate ligands expressed on the parasite surface, like the Lewisx-related molecules, and cell-adhesion molecules like selectins that have, been demonstrated on schistosomula(Behm and Ovington(2000).

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